

CASE REPORT

Comprehensive prosthetic rehabilitation using Emax, PFM bridges, and flexible RPD: A case report

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Abstract

A 48-year-old partially edentulous female patient presented to the dental clinic asking for oral rehabilitation for her missing teeth and adjustment for her current dentures. Upon examination, root fragments of her maxillary right canine (#13) and maxillary left first premolar (#24) were found and extracted to proceed with prosthodontic treatment. The evaluation also showed that her present dentures on the first quadrant were unfit for use. As a replacement, new flexible dentures were indicated and later on fitted. Other edentulous areas, namely her second, third, and fourth quadrants, were supplied with fixed partial bridges. The material used for the abutments and pontics were porcelain-fused-to-metal crowns. Apart from her missing teeth, the patient also had a discolored zirconia crown on her maxillary right central incisor created by her previous dentist. The patient did not want this removed. Instead, an E-max crown was attached to the adjacent maxillary central and lateral incisors. The combination of these treatments was able to meet the patient's functional and esthetic demands.

Keywords prosthodontics, cosmetic dentistry, dental esthetics, tooth extraction, partial denture, fixed partial denture, zirconia, dental porcelain

1 | Introduction

Torresyap et al claimed that a significant proportion of adults living in developing nations are continuing to lose teeth likely due to untreated caries and periodontal diseases and

will probably remain partially or completely edentulous.¹ Being partially edentulous can compromise a patient's eating habits, speech, and appearance. Tooth loss also appears to impact self-confidence, and restrict

Figure 1. Diagnostic tools including (A) panoramic radiograph and (B) diagnostic casts

social activities and interpersonal relationships.² Through the advent of research and innovation in Dentistry, now there are ways to restore oral function while maintaining a pleasing appearance. Prosthodontics emphasizes the diagnosis and treatment planning of patients with complex dental needs, providing treatment services, primarily repairing

or replacing natural teeth with various fixed or removable prosthetic options.

According to a study by Mazurat, patients seek treatment with cast removable partial dentures to improve their appearance and masticatory function.³ Although for many years, conventional fixed bridgework was considered the best treatment option, with an estimated

75% survival rate after 15 years.⁴ With time, the demand for metal-free ceramic restorations has increased to avoid the disadvantages of unaesthetic metal appearance, especially in anterior teeth.^{5,6} The most common metal-free restorations recommended nowadays are zirconia and e-max lithium disilicate crowns.⁷

This case study was focused on gathering baseline data from a 48-year-old female patient, whose chief complaints were missing teeth and a loose denture. The patient demanded to utilize the time as much as possible due to her foreign residency and unforeseen circumstances experienced at the time. Considering the patient's situation, the application of an E-max crown, fixed bridge, and flexible denture were the best available options offered by the dentist. The procedure revealed that prosthodontics can serve as a means of restoring oral function and maintaining esthetic display.

2 | Case presentation section

2.1. Examination

A 48-year-old female patient presented to the dental clinic with a chief complaint of missing teeth and a loose flexible denture. She was self-conscious about her appearance and wanted to have a full-mouth

rehabilitation. An initial evaluation of the patient revealed a history of smoking tobacco and high blood pressure. Oral hygiene was fair, and there was no periodontal problem.

Clinical and radiographic examinations and diagnostic casts revealed the presence of root fragments on Tooth #13 and #24. Tooth #11 was endodontically treated and restored with a zirconia crown. Several teeth were missing, namely #16, #15, #14, #25, #26, #36, #46, and #47 (Figure 1). A diagnosis of Kennedy Class 3 Modification 1 was made for the maxillary and Kennedy Class 2 Modification 1 for the mandibular.

2.2. Treatment

During the first appointment, treatment options were discussed with the patient. A dental implant was recommended, but with the patient's time constraint due to her foreign residency, that option was not feasible. The patient opted for the porcelain-fused-to-metal fixed bridge and for her flexible partial denture to be replaced with a new one. Oral prophylaxis was done and impressions were taken.

Root fragments #13 and #24 were extracted during the second appointment. On the following visit, #35 and #37 were prepared as abutments for the missing #36. Consecutively, #44 and #45 were prepared for the missing #46. Temporary crowns were placed

Figure 2. Treatment procedures. The patient with all the prepared teeth (A). The final Emax crowns, PFM fixed bridges and flexible dentures on the patient's model (B). Smile view of the patient after treatment (C).

afterward. Both fixed bridges will utilize a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown with shade A3. By the next visit, #22, #23, and #27 were prepared as abutments for a 6-unit PFM fixed bridge with shade BL2. Additional preparations were also done for teeth #12 and #21 (Figure 2A). An Emax crown was decided to be placed on these two teeth as requested by the patient, as she was dissatisfied with their color. 2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine was administered during the tooth preparations. By this time, the permanent mandibular PFM bridges were installed and impressions of the lower teeth were taken. Once the maxillary fixed bridge was also done, it was installed in the patient's mouth by the succeeding appointment, and impressions of the upper teeth were subsequently taken. These impressions together with the bite wax registration were used for the fabrication of the

maxillary flexible denture. The aforementioned prosthodontic treatments were used to raise and improve the occlusion of the patient. Figure 2B shows the final dentures fitted onto the patient's model.

Once all the dentures were inserted, the patient was educated on oral hygiene measures and the care of the dentures. A nightguard was fabricated to protect the restorations from any parafunction. The patient was satisfied with the result of the oral rehabilitation, although she was worried that the crowns in her new prostheses might dislodge while she was away. The dentist assured the patient that the materials used were of high quality and that the survival rates are high. The smile view of the patient after treatment is shown in Figure 2C.

3 | Discussion

The case involved the full-mouth rehabilitation of a 48-year-old patient with partial edentulism in both arches which has affected her mastication and confidence in her appearance. The patient previously had a Kennedy Class III flexible denture on her maxillary right quadrant that is now loose. Due to the long span of the edentulous area and insufficient tooth support from the possible abutments, a fixed bridge as a replacement was ruled out.⁸ As the patient is very particular with esthetics, a flexible denture was used. With the translucency of the material that picks

up underlying tissue tones and no clasping visible on tooth surfaces, it is almost impossible to detect in the mouth.⁹

PFM bridges were the treatment done in the three edentulous areas of the patient. In a clinical study by Motta et al.,¹⁰ metal-ceramic FPDs are best indicated in the posterior area where they found a lower failure rate. The underlying grayish shade of the metal is also an esthetic limitation.¹¹ The abutments involved are mostly posterior teeth, therefore PFM was considered a good choice. PFM systems are used mainly when a large number of teeth should be replaced.¹⁰ In this clinical report, a 6-unit PFM fixed bridge was done in the maxillary left edentulous space of the patient. The overall survival after 10 years was 84%, although long bridges have lower survival than shorter ones.¹² A posterior cantilever bridge was also done in this case concerning the missing tooth 46. Applying Ante's law, it can be seen that teeth 44 and 45 can adequately support a first molar pontic.¹³

Because the patient was dissatisfied with the esthetic of her teeth #12 and #21, she opted to have them crowned to match the color of her zirconia crown in #11. Emax crowns were selected in this case mainly because of their ability of bonding to the tooth structure, maximum esthetics from the translucency of

lithium disilicate, and high fracture resistance¹⁴. Malament et al.,¹⁵ reported in a study a 10-year estimated cumulative survival rate of 99.6% for Emax complete-coverage restorations with no failures for incisor restorations.¹⁵

Initially, the patient was recommended an implant-supported prosthesis for her long-span edentulous areas, but with the patient's time constraints in the country, it was deemed impractical. Dental implant technology has advanced significantly in recent years, providing patients with an effective, convenient, and affordable option for replacing missing teeth, but certain requirements are to be met for it to be successful.¹⁶

4 | Conclusions

The patient underwent a full mouth rehabilitation with a treatment plan combining periodontics, surgery, and prosthodontics. A variety of dental prostheses were used namely the Emax crowns, Porcelain-fused-to-Metal bridges, and a flexible partial denture. This offers a combination of strength, durability, and ideal appearance, resulting in greater comfort for the patient by regaining her confidence, restoring masticatory function, and meeting the patient's esthetic demands. After the procedure, the patient revealed that her

expectations were met by the dentist's performance.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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